

DARE UK

‘Virtual’ TREs

Summary Report

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UK Research
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Health Data Research UK

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Data-driven change

Summary Report

‘Virtual’ Trusted Research Environments

1. Executive Summary

This report summarises the work undertaken by a consortium led by the Francis Crick Institute, along with BT plc, the Institute of Cancer Research and the Rosalind Franklin Institute, supported by technical partners Infinite Lambda and Snowflake, to create a technology platform that allows for the creation of secure trusted research environments ‘on-demand’, built around the needs and restrictions of individual research projects. We feel this novel paradigm is an essential part of the technical ecosystem needed to work effectively and securely with sensitive data, and complements more typical ‘data-set-centric’ TRE architectures.

The consortium successfully delivered on the aims of the project, producing a fully working platform that allows the configuration and deployment of secure TREs within around 30 minutes, including novel features such as experimental-level billing control, full audit and management reporting, and HIPAA and ISO27001 compliance. The platform is at the time of writing in use for a first research consortium at the Crick, with another 3 in the process of gaining ethical approvals and agreement sign-offs.

This document sets out the discovery and requirements research, summarises the architecture and technology used to build the working platform, a precis of the legal agreement used as part of research collaboration agreements to complement the platform, and discusses the feedback and immediate impacts seen to date. We conclude with a summary of avenues for future work. This report is supplemented by a series of documents and artefacts which provide considerably greater detail for each section, with a view to making this work as reproducible as possible for any other interested party.

2. Project Genesis

The genesis of this work was the growing issue observed at the Crick that more group leaders were wishing to initiate scientific collaborations with multiple other groups, either academic or within industry, which required increasingly bespoke infrastructure solutions to be delivered by the Information Technology Office (ITO). The complexity inherent in creating secure solutions to meet the demands of handling sensitive data and intellectual property, whilst navigating multiple international data protection regimes and the legal restrictions imposed by the policies of data-owning organisations was rapidly becoming untenable. IT was becoming the delaying factor in science, and such customisation could not scale economically beyond 2-3 concurrent projects. Compounding this problem was the fact that the legal research collaboration agreements had to include complex bespoke annexes summarising data flows, roles and responsibilities between all parties and billing arrangements for use of computing time and resources, and gaining agreements on these factors was proving extremely protracted.

This led the ITO to look for a solution to resolve these competing tensions. As a minimum, it would need to:

1. Allow project-specific infrastructure configurations, but in a common administration environment
2. Enable a common set of roles and responsibilities, allowing for a standard approach to legal terms and conditions regardless of the size or complexity of the collaboration
3. Have native security controls and certifications to meet global data standards, from HIPAA in the US to GDPR.
4. Allow global deployment of infrastructure to meet international data sovereignty requirements
5. Allow access to elastic compute and data resources to cover any conceivable workload and data type, whilst also have sophisticated billing restrictions and controls, recognising that funding for collaborative research is frequently via a mosaic of different grants, each with complex restrictions on spend evidence and no contingency for overspend
6. Have tooling to allow for the import of many different data sets, and allow for the installation and running of many different analysis packages, as well as custom scripting and software
7. Be able to collect metadata to provide detailed audit and compliance reporting and monitoring capability

These success criteria are quite different to what might be termed a 'traditional' set of success criteria for a Trusted Research Environment, which are typically institutional resources built around a sensitive data set which needs to be accessed by researchers internal to that institution, and approved external users. A typical example would be a hospital foundation trust making their electronic patient record system (EPR) accessible in a separate environment for analysis by the hospital's own clinical and research staff.

Our discovery process and work with our collaboration partners confirmed that the challenges faced at the Crick are near-universal and shared regardless of the research area, and are also common between both academia and industry.

We feel that the work we have undertaken here has significant application both nationally and internationally, and this model of TRE delivery has an essential role to play in the target data infrastructure of the UK.

3. Requirements Discovery and Insight

3.1. Discovery Process

The Crick's Business Analysis team interviewed a total of 16 different stakeholders, from 10 different organisations, covering university academia, research institutes, the NHS, telecoms and pharmaceuticals. Each stakeholder mapped to one of 7 main use cases, listed below:

1. NHS working with research
2. University working with peers
3. Enterprise working with healthcare providers
4. Research institute working with peers
5. Enterprise working with research
6. Small institute with (or without) infrastructure working with peers
7. Singleton lab without infrastructure working with peers

The interviewees were selected to represent as broad a set of potential users straddling multiple research councils, organisation types, industry and public healthcare to try and achieve as representative a set of challenges as possible.

3.2. Patient and Public Engagement

In parallel to the discovery interviews, a series of patient and public engagement sessions were conducted by the principal investigator. The panels were organised in two series, via both the School of Neurology at UCLH, and the Royal Marsden Hospital, and contained groups of volunteers responding to adverts for participation posted on their respective notice-boards. Demographic data is not available for these groups, but did contain some former scientific academics, former clinicians and an active member of a hospital research ethics committee.

As a result, the feedback from these panels cannot be said to be fully representative of the public at large, but nonetheless contained very interesting and well-informed perspectives, some of which directly inform the suggestions for future work in section 7

3.3. Summary of Insights

3.3.1. Discovery Interviews

The full report from each interviewee is available as a separate document, but their feedback was collated into 12 'challenge areas':

Discovering Research Opportunities	5	As a researcher, it is difficult to find relevant structured datasets that might advance my own research. Typically, this is because data is generated for a one-time research project purposes.
Research Collaboration Agreements	8	As the legal team supporting research, collaboration agreements are always unique, often because of data or technology differences, and require input from multiple parties, so take time to get right. As a researcher, the lengthy setup time for collaboration agreements slows the ability to start research discovery
Intellectual Property	6	As a researcher, IP constraints written into legal agreements, including expectations from Industry partners, could limit my need to collaborate freely. Tracking what data and results are connected to IPR is hard.
Collaborator Access	7	As a researcher or industry body, it is difficult to quickly & securely access an approved platform to access and share sensitive data assets. And to track and discharge controls signed up to in the agreement.
Aggregating Data	8	As a collaborator, aggregating data from multiple sources (new or existing databases, TRE's, public repositories) is challenging. As a consortium, separating out roles to audit and govern is a challenge
Data Loading	5	As a researcher, loading and off-loading large or sensitive data is difficult. Data transfer rate and volume dictates where to do research. Toolkits differ and refining formats in a secure place is often necessary
Data Processing	5	As a researcher, the data analysis, processing and running code or pipelines I can access is limited by the organisation or body I work for/am affiliated to. Maintaining any separation between datasets /experiments is also a challenge
Data Sovereignty	7	The legal rights of data subjects, and data protection requirements, depend on the location in which their data is stored, results in constricted data access for research. Being able to provide secure auditable data controls may make this easier.
Person Identifiable Data	6	Protection of the patient's right to confidentiality is paramount, but this restricts access to valuable research data, especially unstructured data. Being able to work in a preapproved platform may make this easier.
NHS Data Security	7	NHS Data sits behind a wall that is very difficult to penetrate. Researchers are in the hands of individuals determining what anonymised data facts are shareable, which can often make it difficult to link back or re-use
Audit	7	As a research coordinator, it is difficult to know which collaborators have accessed what data, when. This makes audit and tracking for compliance challenging
Billing	6	Financial controls, and managing computing resources fairly and to project budget, are difficult to manage on cloud-based compute and data storage platforms

3.3.1.1. *Discovering Research Opportunities*

The landscape of curated, publicly available datasets is large and complex, but also only a tiny fraction of all research data. The norm for discovery research, given how tightly bounded and specific the experimental questions are, is to custom create data, or to work with known collaborators who have exactly the data needed to answer a given problem.

As such, discovering novel research opportunities is often a lengthy and involved process, and where public repositories are used, it's normally as a source of verification, so for example if a pattern is found within a small sample, looking to see if that pattern is found in a much larger cohort. In a discovery research context, it is extremely rare that a public repository would contain exactly the right data needed, or solely the data needed to fulfil the needs of a researcher.

3.3.1.2. *Setting up research collaborations & data sharing agreements*

In a post-COVID world, there is much less tolerance for lengthy processes and bureaucratic delays involved in setting up novel research collaborations. Stakeholders and researchers have now seen what can be done in extremis, so are (rightly) intolerant of processes which can add years to the establishment of new research endeavours.

This was the single highest ranked challenge amongst all interviewees, and was a universal theme across all areas – academia, industry, NHS. The delays stemmed from a variety of factors – lack of legal resource being very common, along with unclear decision-making paths and sign-off routes when working with higher risk data. Intellectual Property ownership was another area that caused considerable delays, in particular in partnerships between academia and industry.

Underlying everything however was the highly bespoke nature of every research collaboration – whilst some basic clauses in the legal agreement could be drawn from templates such as the 'Brunswick' standard, there is always a very high degree of customisation required, which is exacerbated when the IT aspects of the agreement have to be started from scratch every time to ensure that the requirements of each data owner is considered and controls put in place to ensure compliance with every parties obligations and policies. The nature of the agreement, especially with regards to roles, responsibilities and liabilities, is almost always constrained by the

availability of whatever IT infrastructure is open to the consortium members, and in extreme cases, may also be the limiting factor in what science can be done.

The time added to the setup of such research collaborations was felt to be in the range of many months, and in extreme cases, sometimes years.

Clearly, not all of these solutions can be fixed with technology, and there will always be a degree of customisation needed in every research agreement, but there are clear gains to be made in having a standard approach to the IT infrastructure aspects, and being able to accommodate a superset of policy and compliance controls within a single platform approach.

3.3.1.3. Multi-party collaborator access

This challenge is one of the fundamental administrative issues with managing a consortium, which is allocating and managing roles and responsibilities for handling, loading and transforming data. Typically, there is no pre-defined framework for these, as they are to a large part dictated by whatever infrastructure is being used by the consortium, which in turn is often distributed across all the consortium members, who are trying to piece together a workable solution from whatever locally available components they can negotiate to use. Often, this therefore means relying on 'best-efforts' support from local administrators for different elements, leading to a lack of standardisation, and considerable complexity in ensuring that the terms of the research collaboration agreement and any ethics approvals are followed correctly.

Having a standardised set of roles and responsibilities known up front, and straightforwardly implemented would have multiple advantages, allowing responsible Group Leaders to know their teams are working in a compliant manner, simplifying negotiations during the collaboration agreement development, and removing the need to 'beg and borrow' time and expertise from local administrators.

3.3.1.4. Data aggregation from multiple sources

The default in discovery research is that the experimental data set to be ultimately analysed will need to be aggregated from many different sources. Some may be sensitive, but a lot won't be. What is almost guaranteed is that a considerable degree of data manipulation will be needed to get a consolidated, fit for purpose final data set. This aggregation can be extremely complex and require both the appropriate skill set and considerable scientific expertise and familiarity with the source data. It also frequently requires environments of appropriate sophistication and security to execute, meaning that in the absence of a common environment, it frequently becomes a patchwork of shared resources between collaboration members to assemble all the required pieces.

Data standards, such as OMOP, would only have utility in a very small proportion of the scenarios faced by the majority of interviewees, such as when patient records from two different hospital trusts need to be joined together. It would have very little utility if this was to be combined with genomic data from stem cells, or image data from mice tissue. In these scenarios, creation of custom schemas and labelling pertinent to the experimental questions becomes much more important. Being able to work effectively with data to achieve this was generally the dominant requirement, not the adoption of global standards.

3.3.1.5. Data sovereignty

Data sovereignty is a direct consequence of many researchers working internationally with peers in different data protection jurisdictions. For example, both Germany and the USA have additional data protection legislation about moving data out of sovereign territory. Simply accessing the data outside of these territories constitutes a transfer, even if the data doesn't physically move.

This can be made possible by incorporating standard transfer agreements into the initial research collaboration agreement, if it's essential that the identifiable data be made visible internationally. This does add unavoidable time and complexity to the collaboration agreement, but if it is identified up front and the terms and conditions are standardised, then this additional agreement time can be minimised. If anonymised data is sufficient, then being able to deploy a 'local to the territory' environment to allow for loading and anonymisation of the data before then sharing across the collaboration is highly desirable.

3.3.1.6. Working safely with patient identifiable data

Working directly with patient identifiable data (PID) is much less common than working with pseudonymised data, but feedback from stakeholders interviewed was consistent that working with either presented considerable challenges. Rather than being one specific issue, PID presented challenges and restrictions across the whole lifecycle of a research project, from the time and complexity of the collaboration agreement, to the level of security needed for the research infrastructure, to the enhanced level of risk and compliance that the Principal Investigators were required to take on.

The lack of accepted standards and platforms for working with PID, both nationally and internationally, places the burden of risk management almost entirely with the PI. In addition to an excellent understanding of the ethics of research with such data, they must also have a very good technical understanding of international data protection law, be able to guide legal professionals in the creation of robust agreements, and also understand the minutiae of information technology infrastructure to ensure that they are discharging their accountabilities effectively. Taken together, this represents too much risk for many, and acts as a barrier to entry to doing research with PID, or even with anonymised patient data.

There is a clear need to de-risk this obligation to promote more effective research with such data, and standardised infrastructure, with effective associated processes, is a significant part of the solution.

3.3.1.7. NHS Data Security

Patient Identifiable Data and NHS Data Security are of course inextricably interlinked. The specific challenge which was identified around NHS Data Security however was its federated nature – ie every hospital or other organisational body has its own processes and policies, along with varying degrees of resourcing given to legal and information security. How access is requested, what constitutes acceptable release of data, and how it will be managed vary from organisation to organisations, once again introducing considerable complexity and lengthy delays into the collaboration agreement processes.

The lack of resource to handle research collaboration agreements, and the lack of an agreed risk framework was also highlighted as a serious issue – often legal and infosec resources are understaffed, and the decision-making processes around risk is unclear.

As with several other of these challenges, the issue is very far from being solved by a technology solution, but again, having a standard, repeatable approach allows risk to be considered once, and then made routine for all future requests, helping to expedite the process, at least with an individual hospital. 'Resourcing for research' however was felt to be a fundamental issue across the NHS, and something which will need national policy and budgeting intervention to structurally solve.

3.3.1.8. Securing Intellectual Property

Intellectual Property (IP) was identified by our interviewees as one of the most complex and potentially contentious aspects of drawing up a collaboration agreement. This was especially acute with industry/academic partnerships where the former parties normally operate in a highly secure 'closed' fashion with rigorous in-house controls around IP, whereas the default position of the latter is to work openly, in line with commitments to open

science. This can lead to tensions in forming workable partnerships, and typically has to be resolved up front during the negotiation phase of the research collaboration agreement.

Clearly, this is not going to be wholly solved by a technology solution, but it was felt that removing as many variables as possible, particularly pertaining to information security and governance, and demonstrating clear controls on access and visibility of data, then this could have a positive impact on the timelines for signing agreements.

3.3.1.9. Data loading & preparation

A significant proportion of the experimental effort involved in research is the preparation of data, rather than its analysis. This is especially true of research involving multiple disparate data sets from varying sources. In the absence of common shared environments, then the ‘where’ is often decided by what is most expeditious based on the rate and volume of data generation, rather than what is most convenient or robust.

This frequently leads to complex ‘spaghetti’ data flows being developed in a very clunky manner, driven by whatever resources a research team can lay their hands on, rather than being explicitly designed to optimise the workflow from the outset. This often leads to huge amounts of experimental time being wasted working around the limitations of what is available, either fault-fixing or adapting sub-optimal solutions, rather than focussing on analysing scientific questions.

3.3.1.10. Data processing & analysis – running code or pipelines

Once the data has finally been loaded and transformed into a useful format, the business of actually ‘doing research’ can begin, and typically this analysis is done via code pipelines, either in frameworks such as Nextflow, or via custom code, typically written in Python. The outputs can then be visualised or analysed in a huge variety of ways with different tools and applications, which are dependent on both the experimental questions being asked, as well as the type of data being used.

The clear requirement here is that there be total flexibility to import tools, applications and code into a trusted research environment to suit the needs of a given project, and that there must also be huge flexibility of underlying infrastructure to meet those needs as well. Some popular scientific applications can only run on Windows virtual machines, some on Linux – some are well suited to batch, HPC-style processing, whereas others require an interactive client-model. One size will never fit all use cases, and this was identified as a key limitation of existing TRE or data safe-haven solutions that stakeholders had worked with – the tools usable in such environments were pre-defined and inflexible, severely limiting what can be done within them.

3.3.1.11. Tracking and auditing compliance with standards – HIPAA & ISO27001

As discussed in several of the other sections, the infrastructure often used by researchers is based around the art of the possible, rather than explicitly designed or managed solutions. As such, both proving up front compliance with information security and data protection standards is extremely difficult, as is monitoring compliance with the agreed terms and conditions of both the collaboration agreement and ethical approvals.

This represents both a major source of delay during the up-front legal process, as well as a considerable drain of time and resource to achieve during the project. In some edge cases, for example working with US collaborators on US patient data, a specific certification requirement, such as HIPAA compliance, may represent an insurmountable barrier to the collaboration ever getting off the ground. In such cases, often the only way for researchers to work together is in deliberate siloes, and only sharing completed analysis work, rather than any combination of raw data.

3.3.1.12. Financial controls – managing computing resources fairly and to project budget

Financial control and equitable distribution of IT resources was an especially acute issue for interviewees operating on a mostly or completely grant funded basis, without access to significant institutional resources or funding. Not only was there the obvious problem of ensuring that no one party in a collaboration dominates the use of a resource, the risk management implications of using cloud native solutions, where billing and cost control is entirely the responsibility of the end user, are prohibitive in environments where funding is extremely scarce.

There is a clear need to be able to distribute resources across all parties according to the funding they bring, and for cost and spend caps to be put in place to prevent accidental but very financially damaging unexpected bills.

3.3.2. Patient and Public Engagement

The response from the PPIE panels to our work was overall extremely positive and thoughtful. There was broad endorsement of the aims and objectives of the project, in enabling and accelerating novel research, whilst preserving existing protections and controls. There were also 4 thematic areas which emerged in discussion, prompted in some cases by the potential offered by features on the platform, and in others by a restatement of existing challenges with the research/healthcare ecosystem. Some of these themes are revisited in section 6 as areas to explore for future work.

3.3.2.1. Transparent Research

Both panels expressed the need for a structural solution to the problem of transparency of data usage in research. Whilst existing consent processes and ethics approvals do provide the necessary governance framework, what they lack is an ongoing reporting regime to enable patients to understand how their data is being used, by whom, and critically what research outcomes have been enabled as a consequence of their consent.

It was clear from panel members as well that there is a deficit of trust in existing legal protections without this ability to see ‘on demand’ how data is being used on an ongoing basis. There is no way for a patient or member of the public to know that the original parameters of their consent are being adhered to, or to understand that the promised controls are in place and being properly managed. This was especially true in the case of patients who actively participated in multiple different research projects – tracking consents becomes a patient responsibility, rather than something centrally managed on their behalf.

What interested the panel about the vTRE platform in this context are the reporting possibilities offered by the very detailed metadata logging on the platform. The ability to understand exactly which researchers were working on their data, and to what purpose in a straightforward manner was described as ‘a potential game changer’ by one panel member, but they recognised that this was beyond the scope of the current project, and would present some practical challenges to implement whilst respecting data protection legislation.

Nonetheless, we have identified the creation of a ‘patient data portal’ as a fruitful avenue of future work, and one of the areas to explore in further phases of the platform.

3.3.2.2. Citizen ownership of data

The topic which generated the most interest amongst the panels was the debate around citizen ownership of data. The discussion centred around a general sentiment that patients’ data is not seen by the NHS or any other body as belonging to the patient, but rather as an institutional asset. This manifested in many different ‘symptoms’, from frustrations with the fragmentation of data within the NHS due to federation of IT strategy to local hospital level, lack of transparency around data use, lack of trust in institutional usage to a lack of satisfaction with current models of accountability.

The current scope of this project clearly does not address this problem, but whilst the panels respected and understood the potential improvements that the proposed platform approach would bring to research, it was still perceived as a point solution which skirts the root issue, namely that patient data strategies in the NHS are not patient-centric, and that they do not put the control in the hands of the ‘true’ data owner, namely the patients themselves.

After reflecting on this discussion in the first round of panels, we proposed a future use case for the platform, using the same technical data controls in a different way to create a ‘patient data account’ analogous to a bank account, which would involve the concept of creating an individual data space for every single person in the UK on Snowflake to store any and all records generated (and synchronised) to the NHS, private health providers, devices and apps. The sharing controls of the platform would be put in the hands of the owning citizen, allowing direct visibility and control of exactly what data is shared with whom, in a similar way to management of direct debits in a bank account.

This proposal was very warmly received by the panel, who suggested this should be a priority for consideration in future work.

3.3.2.3. ‘Constitutional’ protection of consent & other ethical considerations

A strong theme across the panels was the sense that legal protections are insufficient mechanisms to genuinely guarantee privacy or security. There was a general cynicism, motivated by high-profile privacy action against various giant tech firms, about corporate motivation, namely that if the reward merited it, regulation could and would be circumvented.

This raised the interesting question of how and if ‘constitutional’ protections could be created, either through governance or technology, to ensure that consent given once for one purpose does not become abused in future – the example was given that if the Crick for example were to spin out a commercial organisation based on science derived from patient data, how would the patient know, and how would they be given the opportunity to rescind their consent?

A similar question was raised about commercial companies acting as suppliers to the NHS. Typically, a patient has no visibility of how or when their data is shared with a third party, and with the massive growth in digital health and technology companies now working with the NHS, anxiety about the possibility of data being misused for non-consented purposes. A similar concern was raised about academic/industrial partnerships, where it was felt that such work, whilst potentially valuable, presented a privacy risk in the absence of patient control and true transparency.

To conclude, the overall sentiment was one of ‘once bitten, twice shy’, and that the sector covering the NHS, research and industry needs to be far more proactive in seeking and winning trust in digital healthcare and research, as even well informed and supportive patients have serious trust concerns and regard current governance and legislation as inadequate.

3.3.2.4. Responsibility and Accountability

A final area of considerable debate was around the model of responsibility and accountability in using the TRE platform, and the wider implications were such a model to be rolled out at scale across multiple institutions. Whilst these are clear for a single institution model, such as the Crick, where the accountability for management of the overall platform, and administration of the environment sits with the Information Technology Office, including access grants and security controls, and the management of the individual data sets sits with the Principal Investigators of the Collaboration, such roles would need clarification were such a service to be offered more centrally, such as by UKRI or the NHS.

Further details of the precise roles and responsibilities for using the TRE are set out in the legal agreement, which is available in full alongside this document, and is summarised in section 4.

4. The Technology Platform

The Technology Platform, or just Platform, describes all of the individual technology elements which comprise the complete solution for building and managing virtual trusted research environments. This section of the document will discuss both the general architecture of the platform, as well as the specific technology choices we have made for each element of it. As with other areas, there is a supplementary detailed document designed for a technical audience to assist those seeking to replicate this work.

4.1. The Inception to Archive (I2A) Process

The journey below describes the backbone process – moving from initial inception of a research collaboration, through to archiving the data at its close. This process forms the core workflow of the platform, and ties together all the main operational functions.

Figure 1 Schematic Process Flow for I2A process

The process is designed to be as straightforward as possible, modelling a research collaboration as a consortium, namely a group of different individuals, each with a different, pre-defined role, each affiliated with a legal entity, typically their university, institute or company. Each entity will have separate funding arrangements – these can be either grant or core funded – the process simply requires that the identifier used, such as a grant ID, or internal cost code, be meaningful to that entity to allow for billing of usage back to it.

Billing against each cost centre is tightly controlled. Principal Investigators or other accountable budget holders can specify precise budget allocations for both the loading accounts, which are private to each entity within the consortium, and the collaboration account, which is open to all consortium members. This control goes down to ‘experimental’ level, allowing a PI to spread a budget across multiple different research questions, without the risk that one mistake from one lab member might use the entire available grant budget. Once a budget cap is set, the platform will send out an automated warning when a threshold (95% by default, but configurable) of that cap is reached, and then shut down any resources when they hit the limit.

Usage is recorded down to individual user and resource level, and tied back to the funding ID specified up front, allowing a precise itemised bill to be produced for every entity in the consortium.

The process also captures region and certification requirements for the data for each entity, which in turn will drive where in the world the accounts for each of the parties are deployed, and to what service level within the Snowflake platform, e.g. HIPAA certification requires ‘business critical’ support.

This data can be captured alongside the development of the research collaboration agreement, and there is a 1:1 match between the data in the agreement, and the data required by each form in the workflow to ensure absolute continuity.

Sign off of the agreement and completion of all the required metadata gates the deployment of the TRE environment, which is built according to a pre-defined architecture and data-model, which is expanded upon in section 4.3. Once the logical architecture is built on Snowflake, login links and passwords are sent to each of the members of the consortium. They then have permissions on the Snowflake platform in accordance with their pre-defined role, for example, the member(s) of each entity with ‘Data loader’ permissions will be allowed to connect their preferred loading tool – we recommend DBeaver for static loading, and Apache Airflow for pipelines – to their account and upload their dataset.

A variety of modify and amend processes allow for management of the TRE, such as adding new consortium entities, or new members to an account, whilst the project is active, although these can only be performed by the owning administrator, and after appropriate amendments to the legal agreement if necessary.

On closure of the project, there is a separate workflow to prompt all parties to remove their data, in accordance with the pre-agreed ownership in the collaboration agreement, and shut down the TRE. The metadata showing the usage on the platform, as well as the configuration are held separately, allowing both reconstruction of the TRE within minutes, as well as precise logs of exactly what work was done, in the event of any future work to replicate, or challenge results.

4.2. Platform Architecture

The platform function architecture is shown below. The architecture is designed to be as technology agnostic as possible, with the potential exception of Snowflake. Whilst it is theoretically possible to build a similar TRE architecture directly on public cloud or on-premises solutions, this would require considerably greater effort, and a separate intermediary layer between the run-time engine and the underlying Infrastructure as a Service platform to recreate the native Snowflake capabilities.

For every other element of the platform, there exist multiple market-leading alternatives which could be deployed. It is highly likely that any organisation looking to replicate this platform would already have one or more existing solutions for different aspects of this architecture.

Figure 2 Conceptual Functional Architecture of Platform

4.3. Technology Choices

The technology choices made for the platform build were driven mostly by the capabilities readily available within the Crick and Infinite Lambda. All are very well known and industry standard Software as a Service applications.

For speed, and quality of execution, we chose to work with ‘off the shelf’ applications rather than purely open-source alternatives. Given this platform will be put directly into use with Crick researchers, it was also vital that we re-used the components of our existing IT architecture to ensure elements such as identity and authentication used current business processes and security parameters.

We would highly recommend any organisation to adopt a similar approach to ensure the minimum necessary work needed to build a functioning platform.

As an exception to this, we have adopted open-source technologies in the extract, transform, load (ETL) function, and following an evaluation of the various market alternatives, settled on two recommendations, based on variety of functionality, ease of integration with Snowflake, and ease of use and maintenance in operation.

- Apache Airflow is the recommended choice for ‘pipeline’ processes where regular data feeds need to be scheduled and managed, such as from data sources which are undergoing continual updates.
- For more ‘static’ use cases where the load of data is ‘one-time’ or very infrequent, then we recommend DBEaver.

4.4. Trusted Research Environment logical structure

Figure 3 Conceptual Diagram of a Collaboration TRE

4.5. Data Process

The TRE collaboration environment is built around a standard process flow, see Figure 4.

- 1) ELT tools enable data to be LOADED into the Database for each ENTITY account. This loading activity is only done by people holding the DATA LOADER role for that account.
- 2) Once Loaded the data can be PROCESSED ready for sharing to the collaboration account and experimentation. This processing is only able to be done by people holding the DATA PROCESSING role.
- 3) Once prepared the data can be SHARED to a collaboration account. This sharing can only be done by people holding the DATA SHARER role.

Figure 4 Process flow of Data within a Collaboration TRE

- 4) Once the data has been shared, then the data can be made available to the users within the COLLABORATION account. To make this happen the data needs to be CURATED into sets in a Science Database ready for use. This curating can only be done by people holding the DATA CURATOR role. Granting access to experimentation areas is also done by the DATA CURATOR role, and so it is this role that conforms to instructions coming from the collaboration steering committee.
- 5) The final EXPLOITATION stage is where the analysis of the combined data is done. This can only be done by people holding the EXPERIMENTER role and done within a specific SCHEMA set up specifically for the authorised experiment. This is where tools such as RStudio may be deployed and connected to the datasets. This is where data created by the Collaboration will be stored (in SCIENCE database) and where material for Journal publications will be based.

4.6. Types of Data

The Snowflake platform supports all data types and can hold and enable querying of the data in JSON format. Structured data and unstructured data are held in databases, or as external tables. ELT / ETL tools will map such data into the snowflake type automatically, and database DDL SQL syntax can be deployed to set up and modify table formats if or when specialist tailoring is needed.

Image and other binary files are held in staging areas. Two options exist, 1) internal S3 AWS containers or ii) External mounted S3 AWS containers. Both of these are provided for in the build of the Account. The difference is that the Internal S3 stage is inherently enabled at account creation time. The external S3 needs to be configured manually through support of the *admin team*.

Snowflake also provides the opportunity to define data types. And a variety of knowledge content is available to support these features (a few are listed here):

- Data Types: <https://docs.snowflake.com/en/sql-reference/intro-summary-data-types.html>
- Semi-structured data : <https://docs.snowflake.com/en/user-guide/semistructured-concepts.html> like JSON/XML/Parquet/ORC/AVRO
- Binary data: <https://docs.snowflake.com/en/user-guide/binary.html> (image files etc)

4.7. Data Governance and Control

Within the developed eco-system control of the data is done in a variety of ways. No restrictions are placed on the types of data held nor the table formats. Instead, the principles embedded in the collaboration agreement and laws and regulations provide an operating framework. In addition, best practice is fully encouraged and nothing in the configuration does, and should, stop that.

The designed platform supports governance is through three key areas:

- 1) Approvals
- 2) Roles
- 3) Facilities

4.7.1. Approvals:

No person can be created without an auditable approval trail replicated in two places - the workflow ServiceNow platform component and in the logs held on the implementation template code and the snowflake platform.

No native snowflake capability is available to users to create other users. The Accountable Person role is the authorisation.

4.7.2. Roles:

The flow of data shown in Figure is enabled through five different roles:

ENTITY ACCOUNT

- 1) DATA LOADER
- 2) DATA PROCESSOR
- 3) DATA SHARER

COLLABORATION ACCOUNT

- 4) DATA CURATOR
- 5) EXPERIMENTER

Each stage requires the specific role to be used. If the same person is given all roles, then to do anything malicious they will have to consciously change their role for each stage. The full audit metadata inherent in the platform will mean this will be identified and action can be taken.

4.7.3. Facilities:

The Snowflake platform offers two different types of account: 1) Enterprise and 2) Business Critical. If ISO27001 or HIPPA standards need to be met then the account is created with the Business Critical type, which has the necessary controls and security facilities to support this.

Snowflake also comes with extensive metadata capture which is transparent and available in a standard format across all databases. This means that all logins, table access, sql statements run etc is timestamp recorded and exposed to SQL just as other data would be. So, querying of this metadata will allow the development of algorithms to identify and report activity that is deemed "risky".

Snowflake also offers on-platform running of python and java routines. This enables more advanced data processing algorithms to be deployed connecting other facilities and approaches not native to SQL. These have been used to bring all the metadata from all the information tables together in one place and for this to be kept for longer than the snowflake "out-of-the-box" holding time (normally 365 days). As such all the audit and compliance metadata can be assured into a repository to help with Research Data Management (RDM) and similar activities.

4.8. Snowflake Data Tools

The TRE platform is designed to have the same set of specific facilities for each account type.

ENTITY Accounts:

For the ENTITY Account type there is always:

A database called <<Account Name>>_DB. This is where the loaded data resides in tables and where the processed data would also sit. This is the database that would have shares made from it to other accounts.

A database called ACCNT_ADMIN_DB. This is an administrative database and not accessible by any of the users of the account. It is used by system resources to maintain a full copy of all the native snowflake metadata on usage and object information. This is the base source of the data that feeds the master Organisation wide equivalent database that supports Reporting.

To process any data in the TRE a compute facility is needed. Each role has its own. These compute tools are not needing to be known by the users, they are automatically connected by the platform. However, if remote tools are used then the connectors often require the specification of the compute “warehouse” to be used. These are named as

DATA LOADER: <<ACCOUNT_NAME>>_DL_XS_WH
DATA PROCESSOR: <<ACCOUNT_NAME>>_DP_XS_WH
DATA SHARER: <<ACCOUNT_NAME>>_DS_XS_WH

COLLABORATION Accounts:

For every share made to the Collaboration an IN_SHARE database is required. This IN_SHARE database will be used by the DATA CURATOR role holding person to provide access to the shared data. It acts a little like a transparent pipe enabling the COLLABORATION data to see the shared data. It is not a copy of the data, the master of which remains in the originating ENTITY account.

The naming convention for these IN_SHARE databases is: <<ENTITY_ACCOUNT_NAME>><<SHARE_NAME>>

These IN_SHARE databases are not accessible to the EXPERIMENTER role, only the DATA_CURATOR. There is then a further two databases:

A science database called <<ACCOUNT_NAME>>_SCIENCE_DB. This is the database the EXPERIMENTER roles people use to develop the results of the collaboration. This database has specific SCHEMA designs, with a separate schema for each approved experiment.

The second, called ACCNT_ADMIN_DB, performs the identical function as for ENTITY accounts, bringing together a full historical record of what was done in the COLLABORATION account. Again, it is not accessible by people, and only used by the system.

Again, there are compute “warehouses” for each of the two roles:

DATA CURATOR: <<ACCOUNT_NAME>>_DC_XS_WH
EXPERIMENTER : <<ACCOUNT_NAME>>_EXP_XS_WH

4.9. Audit and Compliance Data

4.9.1. Metadata:

As already discussed the TRE platform provides a transparent full set of usage and information metadata. These are all brought together for each account in the METADATA_DB and then collected at the platform level in copies within the ORG_ADMIN_DB.

These separate information and usage metadata tables have been used to provide an audit and compliance data model, see Figure 3. It shows Billing information in yellow and usage information is green. Data objects are shown in Grey and cover Columns in Tables in Schemas in Databases. In addition, in grey, are all the users, their login and the sql they instructed the platform to run (be it through remote tools or native on the platform).

In Blue are tables that are additions to the native Snowflake facts. A set of people is derived from the combined users, the set of accounts is held, and also the budgetary information entered in the configuration and setup phase (and any in life changes) is held. The platform offers the ability to TAG data - see 4.11 Tagging Data.

Figure 3: Metadata model of the Platform usage and information data

4.9.2. Data Flows:

To facilitate the collection of the metadata to support reporting and to record who did what when and what objects existed in the TRE accounts, two additional roles are enabled. These are not accessible to users and are used by the system.

The roles are:

- a) ACCOUNT_REPORTER
- b) ORG_DATA_CURATOR

The ACCOUNT REPORTER role is used to access the METADATA_DB in each account. It has read, but not write, privileges on all the Information and Usage metadata collected there for the account (ENTITY or COLLABORATION).

The ORG_DATA_CURATOR role is used by a central system platform account (The ORG_ADMIN_ACCOUNT) to access the METADATA_DB through shares or replications to it.

The computing associated with collecting and curating this key metadata is done using a hidden system compute “warehouse”. The costs of this activity is covered by a low level % “tax” on the credit budgets provided in the agreement.

4.10. Reporting

In normal operation a TRE will not see the usage information except through a standard cloud-based web reporting tool. At present this is implemented within PowerBI. No account will be needed for PowerBI but the costs associated with providing a licence through the Crick may be charged back.

This single reporting tool that implements a Row Level Security model, offers access to audit and compliance information. Only people with ACCOUNTABLE PERSON or BOARD MEMBER roles will see a set of reporting tool interfaces that help with monitoring activity and discharging audit and compliance roles outlined in the legal collaboration agreement, as well as good governance methods.

This tool is to be found at this URL: <https://app.powerbi.com/groups/d7b42544-803b-4db3-99d5-a32f89d7e440/reports/a655e6a7-1151-40b2-94fc-d6b7a1a59d20/ReportSection02cc206c8cebce6b82dd>

The areas provided are:

- 1) What any individual in a collaboration organisation can see: Based on the account the person is responsible for they will see the users approved and the roles and platform components they have access to.
- 2) Who is involved in a collaboration: What roles people have, what
- 3) What logins have been made? Who has logged in when, how many times have they failed, how did they login?
- 4) Usage levels: What usage has been made of the compute and storage facilities. What the storage capacity is by table name and database?
- 5) What money has been spent: How much cost has been incurred?

Additional reports can be provided as they are developed and will be provided through the same application / tool.

The data model within the reporting tool is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Data model for reporting

The overarching process for the report creation is shown in Figure 5 Top-level components and flows for Reporting Audit and Compliance

. The Org Admin account holds all METADATA from all the individual accounts across the Snowflake platform. Views are created in that database to present the objects shown in Figure 4 Data model for reporting

. These Views are “copied” into the powerBi world to replicate the equivalent data model as shown. The permissions table uses the Microsoft UserPrincipalName() – obtained from the identity management stage and the Azure Active Directory, see section XXX (identity) - to filter the data to just those required by that person based on the roles they have been granted to have. The screens have filter tools which on selection act as filters. The charts and visuals are themselves active filters allowing “click” selection filtering.

Figure 5 Top-level components and flows for Reporting Audit and Compliance

4.11. Tagging Data

The underlying Snowflake technology supporting the TRE platform offers tagging of data objects at a variety of levels. See this knowledge article: <https://docs.snowflake.com/en/user-guide/object-tagging.html>

However, a set of reserved tags have been defined for within the platform developed, see Figure 6.

Name of TAG	Area Type	Focus	Comments and Description rationale
Personal Identifier	Sensitive Data	Column	Anything that refers to a individual (but not spatial address) even if pseudonymised or anonymised.
Personal Data	Sensitive Data	Column	Info about them – spatial Address / health facts / IP address etc
Output	Source of Data	Table	The tables created as part of the experimentation. Probably including the tables shared to Coll account
Input	Source of Data	Table	The tables loaded into an Entity Account - prob including the ones by Data Processor role
Target Outcome	Experiment	Column	The fields representing the Outcome designated variables
Target Predictor	Experiment	Column	The fields being investigated for influence over the outcome variables
Experiment?	Experiment	Column	The experiment label (use the experiment name or ID if possible)
Mod_Test_Val	Experiment	Table	Not sure this is possible to separate out sets (if not in a view or table) for Model / Test / Validation
Used_in_Model	Experiment	Column	Y / N and or the Model name in which it was used
Diagnosis	Science		
Gene_name	Science		
AssayType	Science		
Level of Sensitivity	Sensitivity Data	Column	
Consent Field	Sensitivity Data		

Figure 6: Tagging architecture for TRE platform - reserved models to be applied by participating entities

The application of tags can be done within native Snowflake SQL or through the use of commands passed by functions.

4.12. Naming Conventions:

In order to match certain data up strict adherence to naming conventions will be needed. This is because some of the “joins” desired are not explicitly possible within the systems Snowflake.

For a SubAccount called <<NAME>> the objects are labelled in Table 1.

The key is to ensure transparency to the user and also to enable derivation code, using named objects, to relate them to ROLES and therefore People who have access to them. By aligning all the objects names with the roles more control is provided.

Additional naming conventions, within the processes that move data from the different parts of the system ecosystem (Service Now, AWS flows, Snowflake, GITHUB etc), also helps to ensure that the readability and traceability is maximised.

Type of Object	NAME	Description
Database:	<<NAME>>_DB_INSHARE	For INSHARES form other accounts involved in the collaboration. This is only relevant for COLLABORATION accounts
Database:	<<NAME>>_DB_SCIENCE	The Database within which all Science analysis is completed and results stored.
Database	<<NAME>>_DB	The database used by the ENTITY to land their loaded data, process this into an transformed form, and this is the database that is the source of the data to be “Shared” or “Replicated” to the collaboration account involved.
Compute (Warehouses)	<<NAME>><<2 letter role>>_XS_WH	The two letter roles are DL = Data Loader (Entity Account)

	<<NAME>>_EX_XS_WH_<<EXPT NAME>>	<p>DP: Data processor (Entity Account)</p> <p>DS: Data Sharer (Entity Account)</p> <p>DC: Data Curator (Collaboration) Account</p> <p>EX: Experimenter (Collaboration Account)</p> <p>For the experimenter roles the specific EXPERIMENT name will be added to the end.</p> <p>The WH refers to Warehouse</p> <p>The XS signifies Extra -Small and is the initial default size of the compute on start-up.</p>
Resource Monitor	<<NAME>>_RM_<<2 letter role>>	<p>The resource Monitor associate with the COMPUTE resources for the role. The two alpha shorthand for the roles are the same as those used for the Compute objects.</p> <p>RM stands for resource Monitor</p>
Resource Monitor	<<NAME>>_RM_ACCNT	The Resource Monitor associated with the ACCOUNT overall (including all compute and storage)

Table 1 Naming Convention for different Snowflake objects

5. Legal Agreement

The Legal Agreement is structured with three 'layers', as per the diagram below:

The structure of the legal agreement is three nested sections. At the top level is the Collaboration agreement, largely based on a 'Brunswick' style pro-forma, but with enhanced wording to encapsulate the data sharing arrangements, and any data transfer arrangements where access across sovereign borders is unavoidable. The next level are the Crick Terms of Service and Order Form, which captures the input data for the collaboration, and sets out the obligations and roles of every party, including the Crick's role as overall administrator of the platform. Finally, there are the Snowflake platform terms and conditions, derived from the Snowflake Master Services Agreement.

The elements in blue are therefore designed to be 'lift and shift' from one agreement to another, with it simply being the case that the consortium members have to nominate individuals and budgets in accordance with the overall framework, rather than starting from scratch with every agreement. The data captured in the purple and blue sections directly maps, field to field, to the key metadata in the platform workflow, allowing a very straightforward data entry process, with complete concordance of what is built in Snowflake with what is agreed upon in the legal document.

6. Feedback and Impact

Each interviewee was given a demo of the platform, and then received a questionnaire to give feedback against each of the challenge areas. Across the board, the interviewees felt we have made considerable strides in addressing those challenges, with the biggest impacts made in aggregating data and ease of collaboration.

Discovering Research Opportunities	5	4	As a researcher, it is difficult to find relevant structured datasets that might advance my own research. Typically, this is because data is generated for a one-time research project purposes.
Research Collaboration Agreements	8	5	As the legal team supporting research, collaboration agreements are always unique, often because of data or technology differences, and require input from multiple parties, so take time to get right. As a researcher, the lengthy setup time for collaboration agreements slows the ability to start research discovery
Intellectual Property	6	5	As a researcher, IP constraints written into legal agreements, including expectations from industry partners, could limit my need to collaborate freely. Tracking what data and results are connected to IPR is hard.
Collaborator Access	7	2	As a researcher or industry body, it is difficult to quickly & securely access an approved platform to access and share sensitive data assets. And to track and discharge controls signed up to in the agreement.
Aggregating Data	8	3	As a collaborator, aggregating data from multiple sources (new or existing databases, TRE's, public repositories) is challenging. As a consortium, separating out roles to audit and govern is a challenge
Data Loading	5	3	As a researcher, loading and off-loading large or sensitive data is difficult. Data transfer rate and volume dictates where to do research. Toolkits differ and refining formats in a secure place is often necessary
Data Processing	5	3	As a researcher, the data analysis, processing and running code or pipelines I can access is limited by the organisation or body I work for/am affiliated to. Maintaining any separation between datasets /experiments is also a challenge
Data Sovereignty	7	4	The legal rights of data subjects, and data protection requirements, depend on the location in which their data is stored, results in constricted data access for research. Being able to provide secure auditable data controls may make this easier.
Person Identifiable Data	6	3	Protection of the patient's right to confidentiality is paramount, but this restricts access to valuable research data, especially unstructured data. Being able to work in a preapproved platform may make this easier.
NHS Data Security	7	4	NHS Data sits behind a wall that is very difficult to penetrate. Researchers are in the hands of individuals determining what anonymised data facts are shareable, which can often make it difficult to link back or re-use
Audit	7	3	As a research coordinator, it is difficult to know which collaborators have accessed what data, when. This makes audit and tracking for compliance challenging
Billing	6	2	Financial controls, and managing computing resources fairly and to project budget, are difficult to manage on cloud-based compute and data storage platforms

Biggest impact areas

The biggest perceived impact areas were **Collaborator access, Aggregating data, Audit and Billing**. These were all core features all the way from the very first concept design, so it was pleasing to see that they have had the impact we hoped. There was also significant perceived impact on the simplification of research collaboration agreements, data sovereignty and NHS data security. In each of these cases, the interviewees noted that whilst this isn't (and never could be) a complete solution, having consistency and repeatability in the technology layer of an agreement does considerably reduce the administrative challenge, and reduces perceived risk.

Marginal gains

Our federated cloud-based TRE had little perceived impact on **Discovering Research Opportunities and Intellectual Property**. Discovering Research Opportunities was not a challenge we originally set out to address, but could be improved by widespread adoption of this platform, and sharing via the data marketplace. However, the same is true of virtually any technology. Intellectual Property ownership is generally part of the Research Collaboration Agreement, and IP might be part of the reason why the perceived 'after' pain for Research Collaboration Agreement is not lower. Negotiating IP is a collaborative and complex process, often with significant commercial implications particularly in translation or industry partnerships. There will likely never be a one-size-fits-all solution due to the nature of discovery research, but might be an area that benefits from more legal standardisation and widely accepted risk approaches.

Other insights

The Challenge with the largest spread of 'before' pain was **Data Processing**, reflecting the variety of skills and 'home' data infrastructure available across the research/industry/public sector ecosystem. Other challenges with

a broad spread of 'before' pain include, **Audit, Billing and Person Identifiable Data**. This most likely reflected the range of use cases and stakeholders, which covered very different roles from Director/Group Leader managerial level, to hands-on 'do-ers'.

7. Future Work

7.1. Project Pipeline

At the time of writing in August 22, there is a pipeline of four major consortium projects lined up to use the platform at the Crick, all currently driven by ‘word of mouth’ as the overall service has not yet been ‘launched’ to the wider research community.

All projects are in the clinical research space, covering a wide range of different disease areas, from cancer, to Parkinson’s disease, to Hepatitis B and schizophrenia. They are all very different in structure – two have a complex international dimension, whereas the other two are ‘domestic’ with UK collaborators only. Meeting their needs without this platform however would be extremely difficult and time consuming, and in at least one case, legislatively impossible.

The first ‘live’ project we expect to be working by Sept 22, with the others expected to start before Apr 23.

We can confidently say that this research would be otherwise prohibitively time-consuming and costly to undertake without this platform at our disposal.

7.2. Platform Enhancements

As work has progressed, we have identified new areas of enhancement and automation, and we fully expect that as the first pilot projects use the platform, that they too will generate new features requests and enhancements

7.3. New work

As previously discussed in the PPIE feedback, in section 3.3.2.2, there was considerable positive feedback about our idea to use this same technology architecture to demonstrate how it can be adapted to create a new ‘patient data account’ model for storing healthcare data.

We have completed a first iteration of a concept design for this on paper, and intend to present a full proposal for funding consideration by the DARE UK programme in the autumn. Our consortium partners have all indicated that they would like to continue working on this project in the event that we are successful, and we will continue working together to embed the lessons learned at each respective organisation.

8. Team Credits and Acknowledgements

Successful delivery of this project has been an immense full team effort, and I'd like to personally thank everyone for consistently going above and beyond to not only realise the conceptual vision, but to deliver to a very high standard of quality and engineering. We would of course also like to thank HDR UK, ADR UK and UKRI for the funding to make this work possible.

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